

**O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI
HUQUQNI MUHOFAZA QILISH AKADEMIYASI**

**ZAMONAVIY CHAQIRIQLAR
SHAROITIDA QONUN
USTUVORLIGINI TA'MINLASH:
MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR**

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy
konferensiya materiallari

T O ' P L A M I

2-JILD

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С Б О Р Н И К

материалов международной научно-практической конференции на
тему:

**ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ВЕРХОВЕНСТВА ЗАКОНА В
УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ВЫЗОВОВ:
ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ
2-ТОМ**

**ENSURING THE RULE OF LAW IN THE CONTEXT OF
MODERN CHALLENGES: PROBLEMS AND
SOLUTIONS**

Materials of the international conference Collection
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platforms, mandatory IT system audits for public finances, and regular staff training in cyber hygiene.

Third, the implementation of digital analytics and artificial intelligence (AI). AI can be used for predictive analysis, diagnosing inefficiencies or budget deviations, early-warning systems for corruption risks, and digital training to analyze public procurement and detect suspicious schemes.

Fourth, inclusive and digital civic participation, including electronic engagement platforms (surveys, participatory budgeting), informing citizens about projects, expenditures, and changes via chatbots, SMS, etc., as well as real-time feedback platforms for budget execution.

Fifth, legal and institutional reforms. This includes updating legislation to reflect digital risks and data openness, establishing independent digital audit institutions, creating the role of a digital ombudsman, and implementing open API standards across government agencies and ministries.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that in the digital age, addressing threats in the budgetary sphere requires not just digitalization, but digital maturity—a stage where technology is combined with transparency, security, and active civil society engagement.

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**THE PROCEDURAL PROCEDURE FOR FILING AN APPEAL
COMPLAINT AND PROSECUTORIAL PROTEST AGAINST
JUDICIAL ACTS THAT HAVE NOT ENTERED INTO LEGAL
FORCE**

***Abstract:** This article analyzes the procedural and legal foundations for appealing judicial acts that have not entered into legal force in the appellate procedure. The article reveals the essence and content of the institution of appeal, its place and significance in civil proceedings, as well as the specific features of full and incomplete appeal. In addition, it examines in detail the range of subjects*

entitled to file an appeal complaint or prosecutorial protest, the procedure and time limits for filing a complaint, the grounds for restoring a missed deadline, the requirements imposed on the form and content of the complaint, the attached documents, the powers of a representative, the prosecutor's protest, the state duty, as well as issues related to filing in electronic form. The author evaluates the institution of appeal as an important procedural guarantee for eliminating factual and legal errors that may be committed by the court of first instance, ensuring a lawful and well-grounded judicial act, and effectively protecting the rights and legitimate interests of persons.

Keywords: *appeal, appeal complaint, appellate protest, court of first instance, judicial act not entered into legal force, civil procedure, procedural foundations, time limit for filing a complaint, restoration of a missed deadline, procedural requirements, prosecutor's protest, representative's authority, state duty, electronic document, legality of a judicial act.*

Аннотация: *Ушбу мақолада қонуний кучга кирмаган суд ҳужжатлари устидан апелляция тартибида шикоят қилишнинг процессуал-ҳуқуқий асослари таҳлил қилинган. Мақолада апелляция институтининг мазмун-моҳияти, унинг фуқаролик процессидаги ўрни ва аҳамияти, тўлиқ ҳамда тўлиқ бўлмаган апелляция турларининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари ёритилган. Шунингдек, апелляция шикояти ёки протестини бериш ҳуқуқига эга субъектлар, шикоят бериш тартиби, муддатлари, муддатни тиклаш асослари, шикоятнинг шакли ва мазмунига қўйилган талаблар, иловалар, вакил ваколати, прокурор протести, давлат божси ҳамда электрон шаклда мурожаат қилиш масалалари батафсил кўриб чиқилган. Муаллиф апелляция институтини биринчи инстанция суди томонидан йўл қўйилиши мумкин бўлган фактик ва ҳуқуқий хатоларни бартараф этиши, қонуний ва асосли суд ҳужжатини таъминлаш ҳамда шахсларнинг ҳуқуқ ва қонуний манфаатларини самарали ҳимоя қилишнинг муҳим процессуал кафолати сифатида баҳолайди.*

Калит сўзлар: *апелляция, апелляция шикояти, апелляция протести, биринчи инстанция суди, қонуний кучга кирмаган суд ҳужжати, фуқаролик процесси, процессуал асослар, шикоят бериш муддати, муддатни тиклаш, процессуал талаблар, прокурор протести, вакил ваколати, давлат божси, электрон ҳужжат, суд ҳужжати қонунийлиги.*

Ensuring the legality, validity, and fairness of judicial acts in civil proceedings is one of the essential features of a rule-of-law state. Any judgment, ruling, or decision adopted by a court can ensure the effective protection of individual rights and freedoms only when it complies with the norms of substantive and procedural law. However, practice shows that a court of first instance may fail to establish the circumstances of a

case fully, may incorrectly assess the evidence, or may make mistakes in the application of legal norms. In such situations, the institution of appeal serves as an important procedural means of restoring legality and justice.

The distinctive feature of appellate review is that it is not limited to a mere formal examination of a judicial act, but also makes it possible to reconsider the case on its merits. Therefore, appeal is of particular importance in eliminating factual and legal errors committed by the court of first instance, reaching a lawful and well-grounded final conclusion in the case, and protecting the violated or disputed rights and legitimate interests of the persons concerned. As an independent stage of civil procedure, the appellate stage contributes to improving the quality of justice by reassessing the results of the case examined in the court of first instance.

The most fundamental aspect of appeal is the re-examination of the case on its merits for a second time in the course of reviewing the judicial decision.

“The need to allow cases to be examined twice is explained by the fact that judges may commit deliberate or inadvertent errors when resolving cases, and such errors require correction.¹”

“As a result of such a second examination of the case on its merits, its factual aspects are considered to have been fully and correctly established, since the shortcomings and errors of the lower court are, in most cases, naturally eliminated during a new hearing of the case in appellate proceedings.²”

After appellate review, the legislator grants the right to apply to the review instance court. This court examines judicial acts not by reconsidering the case on its merits, but only from the standpoint of whether the rules of law have been applied correctly.

Thus, only the courts of first instance and appellate (or cassation) instance consider the case on its merits. The content of the appellate

¹ Васильковский Е. В. Курс гражданского процесса. Т. 1. С. 182.

² Малышев К. И. Курс гражданского судопроизводства. Т. 2. С. 77.

court's activity in examining the case on the merits for a second time depends on the type of appeal established by law.

Since the issue concerns the repeated examination of a case, that is, its consideration for a second time, it is important to bear in mind that the activity of the court of second instance does not arise by itself. It is carried out by the appellate court only where an interested person has filed an appeal complaint or protest. In turn, an appeal complaint (or protest) cannot be filed in the absence of a decision of the court of first instance.

As A.Kh.Golmsten rightly emphasized, the emergence of a procedural legal relationship in the higher (appellate) court is caused by an incorrect judgment of the lower court (the court of first instance), while the basis for the emergence of the procedural legal relationship in the appellate court is the filing of an appeal complaint or protest. The new legal relationship differs, in its elements and content, from the procedural legal relationship that existed in the court of first instance¹. S.M.Mikhaylov advances the view that “the repeated examination of a case does not exist in itself, but rather exists for the purpose of verifying the correctness of the judicial act.”²

A case that has already been decided is examined for a second time by the appellate court for the purpose of verifying the legality and validity of the judicial decision.

It is precisely this requirement of repeated examination that defines the two principal features of the appellate court:

the review of the judicial decision and the consideration of the case on its merits.

In addition, in the theory of civil procedural law, a distinction is made between full appeal and incomplete (limited or legal) appeal³.

Full appeal has its roots in the Roman Empire. As a means of challenging judicial decisions, appeal reached its final formation and

¹ Гольмстен А. Х. Учебник русского гражданского судопроизводства. СПб., 1913.

² Михайлов С. М. Оценка доказательств судом второй инстанции в гражданском судопроизводстве: автореф. дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. М., 2001. С. 19.

³ Борисова Е.А. Апелляция, кассация, надзор по гражданским делам: учеб. пособие / Е.А.Борисова. — 4-е изд., перераб. и доп. — М.:Норма : ИНФРА-М, 2024. с.186

consolidation during the reign of Emperor Justinian (527–565). It was during this period that appellate proceedings took the form of a repeated examination of the case, in which the parties were allowed to submit additional evidence and have it examined directly at the court hearing (*judicium novum*) (paragraph 5).

As for incomplete appeal, as M. Lorenz points out, its origin dates back to the period of ancient Germanic law¹.

These two types of appeal require thorough scholarly research.

An appeal complaint (or protest) filed against judgments, rulings, and decisions of courts of first instance that have not entered into legal force is addressed, by the subjects entitled to lodge such complaint (or protest), to the appellate court. However, the appeal complaint (or protest) is submitted through the court that rendered the judgment.

There are scholarly debates concerning the issue of to which court an appeal complaint (or protest) should be addressed and submitted. While most procedural law scholars propose that an appeal complaint should be addressed to the appellate court and sent directly to the higher court, others express the view that although it should be addressed to the higher court, it must nevertheless be submitted through the court that examined the case². Legal scholar E.Egamberdiev explains that the main reason for establishing such a rule is, on the one hand, to create certain conveniences for persons participating in the case, and, on the other hand, to ensure that no one may demand the case file from the court of first instance before the expiration of the period established for filing an appeal complaint or protest against a judgment that has not yet entered into legal force³.

¹ Lorenz M. Über die volle Berufung im deutschen und beschränkte Berufung im österreichischen Zivilprozeßrecht // Zeitschrift für Deutschen Zivilprozeß. Bd. 65. 1952 (Heft 3). S. 170. Это журнал немецкого гражданского процесса (т. 65, 1952 г., часть 3).

² Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Фуқаролик процессуал кодексига шарҳлар. -Тошкент: ТДЮИ нашрети, 2010. – 780 бет.

³ Эгамбердиев Э. Суд ҳал қилув қарорлари, ажрим ва қарорларининг қонунийлиги ва асослантирилганлигини текшириш: Ўқув қўлланма. – Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси. – Т., 2016. -24 бет.

In the civil procedure codes of many foreign countries, an appeal complaint (or protest) is addressed directly to the court of first instance that rendered the decision. In particular, Article 321 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Russian Federation provides that appellate complaints and submissions shall be filed with the appellate instance through the court that adopted the judgment¹.

If an appeal complaint (or protest) is filed by a person who is not authorized to do so, the court of first instance shall issue a ruling on returning the complaint (or protest) in accordance with the procedure established by Article 195 of the Civil Procedure Code. A ruling on the return of the application may itself be appealed (or protested).

An appeal complaint (or protest) filed for the purpose of verifying the legality, fairness, and reasonableness of judgments, rulings, and decisions of courts of first instance that have not entered into legal force shall also be submitted directly to the court of first instance in order to carry out the procedural acts предусмотренные in Article 388 of the Civil Procedure Code.

In judicial practice, there are cases where the parties send the complaint directly to the appellate instance. In such situations, the complaint shall be forwarded, according to jurisdiction, to the court of first instance that rendered the judgment. The court of first instance shall perform the actions established by Article 388 of the Civil Procedure Code and register the received complaint (or protest), indicating the date of its receipt.

The purpose of the legal requirement that an appeal complaint (or protest) be submitted to the court together with copies corresponding to the number of persons participating in the case is to ensure that the participants in the proceedings are informed of the content of the complaint (or protest) and are provided with the opportunity to protect their interests. This requirement does not apply to an appeal complaint (or protest) submitted in the form of an electronic document.

¹ “Гражданский процессуальный кодекс Российской Федерации” от 14.11.2002 N 138-ФЗ (ред. от 30.12.2021) (с изм. и доп., вступ. в силу с 01.02.2022)

According to the requirements of civil procedural legislation, the submission of an appeal complaint (or protest) together with copies proportionate to the number of persons participating in the case constitutes an obligation. Where the court deems it necessary, it may impose on the person who filed the appeal complaint or on the prosecutor who lodged the protest the obligation to submit copies of the written materials attached to the appeal complaint or protest in a number corresponding to the persons participating in the case.

The purpose of establishing a time limit for appeal in the law is to ensure the prompt examination of the case by the court of second instance and to provide the persons participating in the case with an opportunity to familiarize themselves with the case materials already examined and, if they disagree with the decision rendered in the case, to file a complaint (or protest)¹.

The subjects entitled to file an appeal complaint or lodge a protest against a judgment of a court of first instance may submit such complaint (or protest) within one month, or send it in the form of an electronic document certified by an electronic digital signature.

When an appeal complaint (or protest) is filed against a judgment, that judgment does not enter into legal force. If an appeal is filed against judgments that are subject to immediate enforcement under Article 266 of the Civil Procedure Code, the enforcement of such judgments shall not be suspended.

In addition to the general time limit for filing an appeal complaint, the law also establishes special appellate time limits. Such time limits include, in particular, the rule that an appeal complaint (or protest) against a judgment rendered under simplified proceedings may be filed within ten days from the date the judgment was adopted.

The right to file an appeal complaint (or protest) arises upon the adoption of the judgment by the court of first instance, and according to the legislation and the Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Фуқаролик процессуал кодексига шарҳлар. -Тошкент: ТДЮИ нашрети, 2010. – 777-778 бет.

the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Certain Issues of Consideration of Civil Cases by Courts in Appellate and Cassation Procedure,” the commencement of the period for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) is calculated, respectively, from the day the judicial act was adopted or entered into legal force¹.

It should be noted that civil procedural legislation provides that, in particularly complex cases, the preparation of a reasoned judgment by the court of first instance may be delayed for up to five days. Even in such cases, the period for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) is calculated from the date the judgment was adopted. This is because the operative part of the judgment is announced in the very hearing at which the examination of the case is concluded.

Where courts of first instance adopt additional judgments referred to in Article 262 of the Civil Procedure Code, the appellate time limits established by the commented article must also be observed. The time limit for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) against an additional judgment is likewise calculated from the date of adoption of the main judgment. According to the above-mentioned Resolution of the Plenum, the period for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) against an additional judgment is also calculated from the date on which the principal judgment was adopted.

In accordance with Article 264 of the Civil Procedure Code, where an appeal complaint (or protest) is filed against a judgment of the court of first instance, that judgment enters into legal force after the case has been considered by the court of appellate instance. This rule also applies where the appeal complaint (or protest) is filed against only a part of the judgment.

If an appeal complaint (or protest) is filed after the expiration of the prescribed time limit, it shall be returned to the person who filed it. However, the law provides for the possibility of restoring the missed time

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг “Судлар томонидан фуқаролик ишларини апелляция, кассация тартибда кўришнинг айрим масалалари тўғрисида” 2024 йил 25 мартдаги 9-сонли қарори / <https://lex.uz/docs/6881055>

limit. A petition for restoration of the time limit for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) shall be submitted by the parties to the court of first instance.

If the persons participating in the case have missed the time limit established by law for reasons that the court recognizes as valid, that time limit shall be restored by the court in accordance with Article 155 of the Civil Procedure Code, and a ruling shall be issued to that effect.

The reasons that may be recognized by the court as valid include circumstances confirming that the persons participating in the case were unable to file the complaint in due time, in particular, illness preventing them from doing so, departure on a business trip, late receipt of the judgment for reasons beyond their control, the death of a close relative, and other substantial reasons. The law does not establish an exhaustive list of such circumstances; therefore, whether the missed time limit for filing a complaint is excusable is assessed by the court on the basis of the actual circumstances of the case¹.

In Resolution No. 9 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 25, 2024, “On Certain Issues of Consideration of Civil Cases by Courts in Appellate and Cassation Procedure,” it is stated that the illness of an individual, his or her family circumstances (the death or serious illness of a family member), as well as other circumstances, may be recognized as valid reasons if they excluded or seriously hindered the filing of a complaint within the time limit established by law.

When the time limit for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) is restored, the court shall decide the issue of suspending the enforcement of the judgment.

If the time limit for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) has been missed without valid reasons, the court of first instance shall issue a ruling refusing to restore the missed time limit. This ruling may be challenged by way of a private appeal, or a private protest may be lodged by the

¹ Фуқаролик ишлари бўйича судга мурожаат қилиш тартиби [Матн] / Х.Ёдгоров ва бошқалар – Тошкент: Baktria press, 2016. -163 б.

prosecutor. If the appellate court finds the complaint (or protest) to be well-founded, it shall revoke the ruling of the court of first instance and restore the missed time limit.

Article 385¹ of the Civil Procedure Code provides that a missed time limit may, upon the motion of the person filing the appeal complaint (or protest), be restored by a judge of the appellate court, provided that the motion is submitted no later than three months from the date of adoption of the judgment and the reasons for missing the time limit are recognized as valid. The restoration of the missed time limit for filing an appeal complaint (or protest) shall be indicated in the ruling on the acceptance of the appeal complaint (or protest) for proceedings.

Article 386 of the Civil Procedure Code establishes the requirements for the form of an appeal complaint or protest, and these requirements are of considerable importance. Failure to comply with them results in the complaint being left without movement.

It must **обязательно** be indicated to which court the appeal complaint or protest is being submitted. If the complainant is a natural person, his or her surname, first name, patronymic, place of residence or location must be specified; if the complainant is a legal entity, its full details must be indicated. Where a protest is lodged by a prosecutor, the prosecutor's postal address must also be stated. In addition, the complaint (or protest) must necessarily indicate the case number, the judgment, ruling, or decision being appealed (or protested), the date on which it was adopted, and the court that issued that judicial act.

An important part of the appeal complaint or protest is the claims of the person filing the complaint or of the prosecutor lodging the protest, namely, the grounds on which the judicial decision is considered unfounded or contrary to law. In presenting such grounds, attention must be paid to the fact that the complaint or protest must remain within the scope of the claim submitted to the court of first instance. Claims that were not examined by the court of first instance may not be included in the appeal complaint or protest.

Among the procedural requirements imposed on an appeal complaint or protest, the petition of the person filing the complaint (or protest), as well as the list of written materials attached to the complaint (or protest), constitute mandatory requisites.

According to civil procedural legislation, since each party bears the burden of proving the circumstances on which it relies as the basis of its claims and objections, it is advisable for the person filing the appeal complaint to attach to the complaint evidence supporting the arguments set out therein.

The appellate court is entitled to examine any evidence, regardless of whether such evidence had been examined by the court of first instance or was newly submitted or requested.

If the appellate court refuses to examine newly submitted evidence, it must state the reasons for such refusal in its ruling.

The appellate court is not entitled to reject motions of persons participating in the case concerning the conduct of an expert examination, the preservation and requesting of evidence, the questioning of witnesses, and other motions solely on the ground that such motions had previously been rejected by the court of first instance.

Evidence shall be examined in accordance with the procedure established for the court of first instance¹.

The procedure and forms for formalizing the powers of representation in court are established in Chapter 7 of the Civil Procedure Code, while the representative's authority to appeal a judicial act has a specific legal character. According to the content of Article 69 of the Civil Procedure Code, the representative's authority to challenge a judicial act must be expressly stated in the power of attorney issued to him or her.

The Resolution of the Plenum further explains that a representative of a person participating in the case, including an advocate, is entitled to file an appeal or cassation complaint against a judicial act only where such

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг “Судлар томонидан фуқаролик ишларини апелляция, кассация тартибида кўришнинг айрим масалалари тўғрисида” 2024 йил 25 мартдаги 9-сонли қарори / <https://lex.uz/docs/6881055>

right has been specifically indicated in the power of attorney granted by the principal¹.

Proceeding from Article 68 of the Civil Procedure Code, representatives of state administration bodies and officials act before the appellate instance on the basis of a power of attorney signed by the head of the relevant body or by the respective official.

A power of attorney issued on behalf of an organization shall be signed by the head of the organization, and the signature shall be certified by the seal of the organization. Heads of organizations shall submit to the court documents confirming their official position or authority.

Where a complaint (or protest) is filed in electronic form, the electronic signature of the interested person must be verified in accordance with the requirements of Article 5 of the Civil Procedure Code.

An appellate protest shall be lodged and signed by the prosecutor or his or her deputies. The term “deputy prosecutors” should be understood to include the deputies of the district prosecutor, the regional prosecutor, and the Prosecutor General.

Certain documents must be attached by persons filing an appeal complaint. One of the important requirements for filing an appeal complaint is the payment of the state duty and postal expenses. A state duty shall be levied, in the manner and amount established by law, for filing an appeal complaint against a court judgment. Pursuant to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On State Duty” dated January 6, 2020, appeal complaints against court decisions are subject to payment in the amount of 50 percent of the rate payable when filing a statement of claim or other applications and complaints². Deferral of payment of the state duty is allowed in cases provided for by legislation. Taking into account the property status of the parties, the court may defer or allow payment by

¹ Ўша манба. 2-банди.

² Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 07.01.2020 й., 03/20/600/0023-сон, 14.03.2020 й., 03/20/610/0299-сон.

installments of the court expenses recoverable to state revenue from one or both parties, and may also reduce the amount of such expenses.

Where a protest is lodged by a prosecutor, documents confirming payment of the state duty and postal expenses are not attached to the protest. Pursuant to paragraph 25 of Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On State Duty,” prosecution bodies are exempt from payment of the state duty in respect of claims filed and applications submitted in the interests of the state, legal entities, and individuals¹.

Article 51 of the Civil Procedure Code provides that the prosecutor is exempt from the payment of court expenses. According to Article 127 of the Civil Procedure Code, court expenses consist of the state duty and costs related to the consideration of the case.

The prosecutor, a higher-ranking prosecutor, and their deputies are entitled to lodge an appellate protest against a judicial act both in cases examined with the participation of a prosecutor and in cases where the participation of a prosecutor is prescribed by law but the case was considered without the prosecutor having been duly notified of the time and place of the court hearing.

Under civil procedural legislation, where an appellate protest is lodged in a case considered without the participation of a prosecutor, a copy of the petition of the persons referred to in part one of Article 383 of the Civil Procedure Code, which served as the basis for lodging such protest, shall be attached to the protest.

Persons filing an appeal complaint (or protest) with the court of first instance must comply with the requirements of Articles 385, 385¹, 386, and 387 of the Civil Procedure Code.

Where an appeal complaint or protest is lodged against a ruling of the court of first instance on the return of an application or on the refusal to accept an application, issued on the basis of Articles 194 and 195 of the Civil Procedure Code, the application returned by the court, together with the documents attached thereto, shall also be appended. If such ruling is

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг “Давлат божи тўғрисида”ги Қонуни, 07.01.2020 й. / “Халқ сўзи” газетаси, №4 (7506)

set aside by the appellate court, the appeal complaint shall be deemed to have been filed on the date of the initial application to the court.

Failure to comply with the requirements concerning the documents that must be attached when filing an appeal complaint (or protest), namely: failure to attach a document confirming the representative's authority where the complaint is filed by a representative; failure of the complaint to be signed by an authorized prosecutor or his or her deputy; failure to submit copies of the appeal complaint in a number proportionate to the number of persons participating in the case; absence of the documents that must be attached to the appeal complaint; as well as failure to submit a document confirming payment of the state duty, shall constitute grounds for leaving the appeal complaint (or protest) without movement by a ruling of the court of first instance.

The court may not interpret expansively the requirements set out in Articles 385–387 of the Civil Procedure Code.

Under the civil procedural legislation of the Russian Federation, if an appeal complaint or a prosecutor's submission does not comply with the requirements provided for in Article 322 of the Civil Procedure Code, and if the state duty has not been paid, the court shall, within five days, issue a ruling setting a reasonable time limit for rectifying the deficiencies¹. It may be observed here that these procedural requirements are similar to those of national legislation; the only difference is that, under our legislation, the issue of within how many days the court must issue a ruling leaving the complaint without movement is left to the court's discretion. In judicial practice, this period is determined by courts of first instance on the basis of the requirement that, within ten days from the expiry of the period established for filing a complaint (or lodging a protest) against the judgment, the case together with the received complaint (or protest) must be sent to the appellate court.

Resolution No. 9 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 25, 2024, "On Certain Issues of

¹ Гражданский процессуальный кодекс Российской Федерации от 14 ноября 2002 г. N 138-ФЗ, 323-статья. (ред. от 30.12.2021) (с изм. и доп., вступ. в силу с 01.02.2022)

Consideration of Civil Cases by Courts in Appellate and Cassation Procedure,” states that a complaint (or protest) which does not comply with the requirements of Article 386 of the Civil Procedure Code, as well as one filed in violation of the requirements of Article 387 of the Civil Procedure Code, shall be left without movement and returned by a ruling of the judge¹.

If the deficiencies indicated in the court’s ruling are remedied within the prescribed period, the complaint (or protest) shall be deemed to have been filed on the date when it was originally submitted to the court; otherwise, the complaint (or protest) shall be deemed not to have been filed. Such ruling shall be delivered to the person who filed the appeal complaint (or protest) against signature, or it may also be sent by post or in the form of an electronic document through the information system.

However, civil procedural legislation does not provide a mechanism allowing the parties to apply to the court for an extension of the period granted for remedying deficiencies where, for valid reasons, they were unable to eliminate the deficiencies indicated in the ruling within the prescribed time. In judicial practice, in such cases the appeal complaint (or protest) is returned. The interested person is then required to apply to the court anew. In this regard, the civil procedural legislation of certain states provides that, where the circumstances indicated in the ruling could not be remedied for valid reasons within the period granted by the court, the court may further extend that period.

If the interested person disagrees with the court’s decision to leave the appeal complaint or protest without movement, that is, if he or she does not accept the grounds stated therein, a private appeal or a private protest may be lodged against the ruling on the return of the complaint in accordance with paragraph 15 of Resolution No. 19 of the Plenum of the

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг “Судлар томонидан фуқаролик ишларини апелляция тартибда кўриш амалиёти тўғрисида” 2021 йил 20 апрелдаги 14-сонли қарори / www.sud.uz

Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 25, 2019, “On Rulings of the Court of First Instance in Civil Cases.”¹.

In conclusion, it may be stated that the principal essence of appeal consists in the repeated examination of the case on its merits simultaneously with the review of the judicial decision, and it is precisely this feature that distinguishes it from other forms of review. At the same time, the appellate legal relationship is not merely a continuation of the procedural legal relationship existing in the court of first instance, but constitutes an independent procedural stage arising upon the filing of an appeal complaint or protest.

Particular attention was also paid to the substance and nature of full and incomplete appeal. It was emphasized that, while full appeal is aimed at an almost entirely new consideration of the case on its merits, incomplete appeal is primarily directed at reviewing the legality and validity of the judicial decision. From this standpoint, theoretical approaches were outlined according to which incomplete appeal appears to be a more effective model for meeting the objectives of modern civil proceedings.

At the same time, important procedural issues were examined in detail, including the procedure for filing an appeal complaint or protest, by whom it may be filed, to which court it should be addressed and through which court it should be submitted, the applicable time limits, the grounds for restoring a missed time limit, the requirements concerning its form and content, attachments, the state duty, the prosecutor’s protest, the representative’s authority, and filing in electronic form. It was substantiated that failure to comply with statutory requirements when formalizing an appeal complaint may result in its being left without movement or returned, and therefore procedural discipline and precision at this stage are of decisive importance.

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий суди Пленумининг “Фуқаролик ишлари бўйича биринчи инстанция судининг ажримлари тўғрисида” 2019 йил 25 октябрдаги 19-сонли қарори / www.sud.uz

The institution of appeal serves as an important guarantee for eliminating factual and legal errors that may be committed by the court of first instance, ensuring the adoption of a lawful and well-grounded judicial act in the case, and effectively protecting the violated or disputed rights and interests of citizens and organizations. The proper application of this institution constitutes an important condition for ensuring legality, fairness, and procedural guarantees in civil proceedings.

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LAW ENFORCEMENT ACTIVITIES IN CYBERSPACE TO COMBAT DRUG ADDICTION: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE, CHALLENGES, AND SOLUTIONS

***Annotatsiya:** Maqolada noqonuniy giyohvand moddalar aylanishining 90 foizdan ortig‘i kiberfazoga o‘tganligi ko‘rib chiqiladi, bu O‘zbekiston uchun milliy xavfsizlikning ustuvor tahdidlaridan biri sifatida tan olinmoqda. Prezident Sh. M. Mirziyoyevning giyohvandlikka qarshi kurashni to‘liq raqamli sohada olib borish haqidagi chaqirig‘i keltiriladi hamda UNODC, Europol va EMCDDAning sintetik giyohvand moddalarni tarqatishda darknet bozorlari, shifrlangan messenjerlar va Telegram-botlarning ustunligi haqidagi xalqaro ma‘lumotlari keltiriladi. Muallif asosiy qiyinchiliklarni tahlil qiladi, jumladan, ilg‘or anonimlashtirish texnikalari, sun‘iy intellekt yordamida avtomatlashtirish, voyaga yetmaganlarni jalb qilish va yurisdiksiya cheklovlari. AQSh (DEA JCODE), Germaniya (BKA ZIT), Europol, Avstraliya, Singapur va Niderlandiyaning eng yaxshi jahon amaliyotlariga tayangan holda, maqolada O‘zbekiston uchun moslashtirilgan kompleks choratadbirlar taklif etiladi. Ularga maxsus kiberbo‘linmalar tashkil etish, xalqaro hamkorlik, yoshlar volontyor monitoringi, ta‘lim dasturlari, reabilitatsiya alternativallari va yillik kiber mashg‘ulotlar kiradi. Ushbu choralar amalga oshirilganda O‘zbekiston 3–5 yil ichida onlayn giyohvand moddalar mavjudligini, ayniqsa yoshlar orasida keskin kamaytirish bo‘yicha Markaziy Osiyoda mintaqaviy yetakchiga aylanishi mumkin.*

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Олий аттестация комиссияси Сизнинг 2025 йил 31 октябрдаги №30/5-180713/25-сон хатингизга жавобан «Замонавий чақириклар шароитида конун устиворлигини таъминлаш: муамо ва ечимлар» мавзусида жорий йилнинг 27-28 ноябрь кунлари ўтказиладиган халқаро илмий-амалий конференция инглиз тилида нашр этилган илмий мақолалар юридик соҳа бўйича докторлик диссертациялари натижаларини чоп этиладиган хорижий илмий журналлардаги илмий мақолаларга тенглаштирилганини маълум қилади.

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